

CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE END OF THE AGE OF CRIMINAL RESPONSIBILITY

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the issue of the end of the institution of criminal majority, in which it seeks to clarify the fact that, given the advances in psychological sciences regarding the behavior and consciousness of individuals in conflict with the law, aware of the risks and damages invoked against themselves and third parties, the maintenance of a legal scope that overprotects this individual, transforming him into someone incapable from a legal and psychological point of view, is contrary to sociological and pedagogical development. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that it discusses a legal issue that has become urgent, from sociological and psychological aspects. Its social relevance lies in presenting to the general public the mechanisms of legal protection for children and adolescents against vulnerabilities that have become instruments of terror and threats to public order. This is a bibliographical essay, based on national and international authors and on the systematic study of Brazilian law, on which the creation and maintenance of such a legal institution was based, whose naive interest is to protect children and adolescents. The aim of this essay is to have a broad and technical discussion about the elimination of the institution of criminal majority, in which delinquents would no longer be judged according to their respective ages, analyzing whether or not they are accountable according to the law; however, they would be subject to arbitrary judgment according to the degree, lethality of their actions and the damage caused by them to third parties. It is concluded that the end of the institution of criminal majority is intended to protect society from the shady interests of groups that have become manipulators of justice, taking as their object of individual protection a cause that, a priori, and in the early days of Brazilian justice, demonstrated [or seemed] to be of a noble nature.

Keywords: Criminal majority. Children's and adolescents' rights. Positive law . Public policies.

INTRODUCTION

The creation of the age of criminal responsibility can *historically represent* a major advance in criminal proceedings and the judgment of offenses and crimes, from the point of view of guaranteeing human rights; considering that, until its institution, juvenile delinquents were tried and interned alongside adult criminals, resulting in serious cases of violence and abuse against the former. Thus, in 1927, Brazil instituted a system of differentiated treatment for offenders according to their age, based on psychological studies that predicted that until the age of 21, an individual could not be held criminally responsible for their actions, as they were still immature from a cognitive standpoint.

As stated *above*, the establishment of an institution that legally defines who can and cannot be judged according to the rigors of the law and based on their actions cannot be seen as a human achievement in terms of values, and even less so from a legal perspective, precisely because it is very subjective at first and quickly becomes arbitrary, forcing law enforcement agents to submit to rhetoric created specifically to benefit lawbreakers, regardless of the magnitude of the offense or crime committed.

This can be understood as a relativization of crime and violence, opening a precedent, *ad infinitum*, for the organization of a world marked by the control of sects and marginal groups that would take this particular condition to produce a parallel state under the command of a sociopathic leader. And this is exactly what happened, especially in Brazil, the target of this study; but when the situation is analyzed as a whole, on a global political scale, the problem has become endemic in all civilized societies, each resorting, in its own way, to mitigate the problem and limit the action of criminal groups that recruit children and adolescents to act as tools of delinquent action, serving their nefarious purposes.

The problem is that, over time, these individuals, once just innocent children, feed off the power that situations provide them and, little by little, transform into true monsters, hidden beneath an angelic face; but whose gaze betrays them as creatures no longer endowed with any sense of humanity; merely figures marked by hatred, anger, and an insane desire for fear and violence that is never satisfied; always seeking more, as if that attitude became an addiction and the half-life of the adrenaline caused by aggression and the terror imposed on others was shortening the more it is practiced.

With the system adopted, where protection is granted to the individual based on their legal category—that is, being a minor and therefore under the protection of legally constituted, imperative force, and thus considered not criminally responsible, regardless of the delinquent

act committed or its recurrence—the entire penal system becomes an object of manipulation, failing to restore to society the level of respectability expected of an organic process. Everything produced around the delinquent is merely *pro forma*, because their legal representative will request the application of the terms of the law, which already classifies them as a child and/or adolescent, describing an entire subjective sociological condition that they should be fully enjoying and exercising. Since they are not in these conditions, it is up to the State to provide them with, to clarify, health and basic education, not to impose sanctions and punishments.

However, in any society, from the most primitive to the most advanced, crime must be rigorously combated so that its practice is not taken as an example by others and impunity is not interpreted as an act of leniency on the part of the State, encouraging its continuation and putting an end to the nefarious interests of criminal organizations that take advantage of these pathetic attributes to carry out their plans to dominate society through the recruitment of children and adolescents, many of them in conditions of social vulnerability.

This essay proposes the abolition of the concept of the age of criminal responsibility, whereby offenders would no longer be judged according to their respective ages, analyzing whether they are or are not criminally responsible according to the law; instead, they would be subjected to arbitrary judgment in accordance with the degree and lethality of their actions and the damage they caused to third parties.

Before any prejudgment is made, the merits of the conviction and the sentencing, as well as its execution, would be subject to the arbitrary determination of the competent judge, after analyzing the reports relevant to the psychological aspect of the individual, issued by whomever is competently determined by the court. The aim of this intervention is to make crime cease to be a *common occurrence* in modern societies.

Regarding the legal concept of the age of criminal responsibility.

The age of criminal responsibility, thus considered, by the principle of legitimacy, to be 18 years old, is established in the Federal Constitution of 1988, in article 228, which states that minors [in this case, the *aforementioned* one] are not criminally responsible and are subject to special regulations. The determination of the age of 18 years is related to the so-called *doctrine of integral protection*, an international guideline created based on the Universal Declaration of the Rights of the Child (UN, 1959; ratified in the International Convention on the Rights of the Child, in 1989), which has as its fundamental principle the recognition that children and adolescents are subjects of rights. Thus, it affirms the value of the child as a human being; the

need to respect their peculiar condition as a person in development; Children and adolescents are seen as an extension of their family and their people, and their vulnerability is recognized, making them deserving of full protection from their family, society, and the State, the latter being the executor of specific policies for the care, promotion, and defense of their rights (Souza, 2002).

Although the aforementioned convention does not specify which age should be chosen [*or adopted*] to define the age of criminal responsibility, it *defines a child as any human being under 18 years of age*. Therefore, Brazil, as a signatory to this treaty, bases its penal system for young people on what is stated in this convention, as an expression of its doctrine. The *doctrine of integral protection* appears most clearly in Article 227 of the 1988 Brazilian Constitution, which speaks of the obligation of the family, society, and the State to ensure, with absolute priority, the rights of children, adolescents, and young people.

Before any further argumentation, it must be clarified that the entire understanding adopted here is based on precepts derived from *yus legis* and not from psychological studies from after the Industrial Revolution and after the Second World War. This is a matter to be discussed elsewhere, when considering the proposition of psychological control of delinquent action under the conscious condition or absence of the conditionality of risk to one's own safety or that of others, which should [*or ought to*] be determined by a specialized professional and not by prescribed determinations.

Andrade Filho (2007) clarifies that,

Initially, *it is necessary* to understand that the age of criminal responsibility is a formally and materially constitutional norm. Formally constitutional simply because it is included in the text of the Constitution. And, materially constitutional because it deals with supra-state law, since this is how criminal liability should be characterized in any State governed by the rule of law. Furthermore, it is inconceivable that the institution of the age of criminal responsibility should not be given the character of a fundamental individual guarantee. This would give the State the opportunity for criminal liability of all kinds, with a great mitigation in the assessment of the capacity for criminal responsibility. Therefore, it is indisputable that the institution of the age of criminal responsibility is a constitutional guarantee given in abstract to each and every citizen against the fury of state power. This is quite different from lending such a protective character of individual guarantee – an entrenched clause – to the starting point for the age of criminal responsibility, because this would be to freeze our legal system in the face of our own social evolution. The fundamental individual guarantee of the age of criminal responsibility, which is an entrenched clause, but displaced from art. Article 5 of the Federal Constitution should be perpetuated, petrified, to forever guarantee the assessment of the *minimum capacity for criminal responsibility*. However, it differs from its initial term (currently 18 years), which not only can but must

accommodate the evolution of society and the law itself (Andrade Filho, 2007, n.p.).

What the author presents in this epigraph is the unquestionable maintenance of the institution of the age of criminal responsibility, considering that its existence represents a social conquest against the abuse of state power against those who do not have the power to decide on their actions. At the same time, he reiterates that its condition is an abstract reason, that is, even if it continues to exist, it may be subject to interference according to jurisprudence and subsequent studies that demonstrate the need or relevance of adjusting the legal understanding of minors and the delinquent acts they commit. What deviates from factual reality is the passionate defense he makes of the semantic application of the *minimum capacity for criminal responsibility*, a condition that cannot be treated as a generic virtual component and as an argument of social representation, because experiential situations of a sociological nature determine cognitive maturation of such magnitude that, in many cases, the minor is fully aware of the dimension of his act and how much he can infer about the emotional state of the other.

In the context of forensic psychology, "consciousness expresses the individual's overall ability to take control, to know, to reflect, not only on the reality that surrounds them, but also on their own psychic state and the relationships between them, their needs, and consequently to conduct their behavior in order to evaluate it once it has been carried out" (González, 2012, p. 41); that is, the issue is that the aggressor, regardless of their age, is fully aware of the extent of the harm caused to another and, in this sense, the protection afforded by documents would be meaningless, requiring a synthetic-analytical investigation to determine the causal link between the crime, the motivations, and the individual's consciousness.

However, it has been conventionally agreed, as a form of comprehensive protection, that a minor is *incapable* , from an intellectual and cognitive point of view, and cannot deliberately be held responsible for their actions before the justice system and the State. This understanding is corroborated by Article 50 of the Military Penal Code, *which states* :

A minor under eighteen years of age is not criminally responsible, unless, having already reached sixteen years of age, they demonstrate sufficient mental development to understand the illicit nature of the act and to act in accordance with this understanding. It can be seen here that the age of criminal responsibility is always guaranteed, but not its starting point, which depends on other elements of culpability. The essence of this constitutional guarantee lies in the preservation, *ad aeternum* , of a reasonable assessment of the minimum capacity for a citizen to be held criminally responsible, that is, only within the framework of the age of criminal responsibility. Outside this essential core is the starting point for this responsibility, as this must be altered whenever social evolution so requires; therefore, it is not covered by the fundamental clause (Andrade Filho, 2007, n.p.).

Unlike what is stipulated in the 1988 Federal Constitution, the establishment of the age of criminal responsibility cannot be considered an entrenched clause, because this would abolish the possibility for society to analyze, interpret, and synthesize crimes, offenses, and consequently, offenders in light of the interpretation of epistemic and scientific advances in the areas of human, social, psychological, and medical (clinical and psychiatric) sciences. Therefore, the magistrate is free to take other measures, according to the circumstances of the criminal act and the specific circumstances surrounding it, the victim, and the perpetrator.

Even though attempts are made to discuss and defend the current regulations, in which the minor has been elevated to the status of a *sacred cow*, not only deemed unaccountable under the legal aegis but also treated as someone incapable of reasoning, deliberately and autonomously, from the moment they break the social contract, all this with the claim that before the creation of the doctrine of integral protection, the judge acted as an arbitrary figure. However, powers were removed from the magistrate and not transferred to any other being, allowing the minor in conflict with the law to be judged according to abstract circumstances, left at the mercy of the interpretation of bureaucrats and generic sociological theories.

All of this would sound plausible if the Brazilian State did not fail its citizens from conception to death, when they are born completely deprived of any kind of medical-sociological assistance [*including medication, clinical-nutritional-vitamin monitoring*], both for the mother and the unborn child. When this individual manages to reach adulthood, being considered an adult, he is, *per se*, a survivor. But, if he proves to be a conscientious and diligent citizen in his duties, he will be an invisible creature in society and, more especially, for the public agents responsible for his abstract guardianship, considering that the objective guardianship of children is the direct and unrestricted responsibility of the parents and/or legal guardians.

In this sense, the existence and maintenance of the institution of the age of criminal responsibility appears as a strange element, if it only serves when the minor becomes a risk to the safety of adults. Even if this passage reveals ambiguity regarding the protection of the minor from the wrath of society, a feeling that clearly reveals a condition of fear, which justifies [*in theory*] the forced removal of the minor from broader social interaction and which leads some to seek to defend them from such an onslaught of fury.

However, what we have witnessed is the State's ineptitude in effectively combating the violence to which children and adolescents are subjected, and its inefficiency in preventing crimes committed by this group, which are constantly, increasingly, recurrently, and repeatedly; always treated as victims of the situation, in which the generating and provoking situation of

evil persists. Thus, maintaining the institution of the age of criminal responsibility proves inept, from both a legal and sociological perspective, since the cause of the problem and its consequent causal link with the deliberate production of juvenile delinquency are known.

Understood in this way, protective action is not justified when considering the *innocent simplicity* of the offender who has been abducted by a monstrous and degrading situation. This becomes a deplorable paradox, leading to the need for more comprehensive and flexible laws that would allow the magistrate to demand, when deemed discretionary, a broad and thorough investigation into the motivations that led the minor to the delinquent act and also to recidivism. As the state apparatus is currently structured, it is up to the judge to determine the investigation; however, their action ends up restricted to the bureaucracy that, by force of law, has already determined which competent bodies will be responsible for carrying out such measures to understand the causes and effects of the means on the child and adolescent ; never the causal link caused by their actions on the environment and on the psychology of those involved.

With the end of the legal age of criminal responsibility, the entire state apparatus, which is currently centralized in bureaucratic bodies governed by laws that are unsustainable when analyzed from a sociological perspective, would be deprived of the power to determine the logic of analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of situations that lead to and drive delinquent behavior committed exhaustively by minors. As it stands, the rhetoric of the eternal victim persists, where the provision of basic necessities can solve [*and even end*] the problem of juvenile delinquency, denying the existence of a very subtle psychological process that must be analyzed in light of other sciences that transcend the indiscriminate logic of deprivation.

Public policies aimed at children and youth and juvenile delinquency.

As is quite natural in a country like Brazil, where everything is politicized in the sense of promoting the group in power and public policies are treated as actions to combat problems created by others, that is, once again the guidelines are geared towards satisfying individual egos and not towards serving a population that is at the mercy of all sorts of misery and social ills, the report released by UNICEF (the UN agency responsible for children and youth) shows that, in 2023, more than half (55%) of the population aged between 0 and 17 years will live in conditions ranging from extreme poverty to misery.

Of the aforementioned population, during the analyzed period, 7.8% had no access to education whatsoever, and 11.2% were homeless. This group is relegated to a condition of social vulnerability and exploited in the most cruel ways imaginable. These children and

adolescents end up being recruited into the world of delinquency in various forms: prostitution, drug trafficking, theft, robbery, human trafficking, and organ trafficking. This is a situation for which the Brazilian State and its entire bureaucratic apparatus cannot present a viable and plausible solution, precisely because the bureaucratic ideological machine focuses on trying to compensate for what cannot be replenished once lost: the individual human condition, due to the absence of affection and security conditioned by family support.

In their ineptitude in the face of the problem, they resort to the tired old cliché that extreme poverty and misery lead these children into a life of crime, committing petty offenses, *a priori*, in order to support themselves in their struggle against *Mademoiselle* Hunger, this lady who refuses to abandon them even in their sleep. As they grow older, they begin to commit more serious crimes until they reach the point of extremely grave acts, ending up imprisoned or dead in conflict situations.

This is a theory that has some truth to it; however, it does not clarify and, to make matters worse, hides the brutal reality of peripheral and underdeveloped countries: the existence of groups specialized in recruiting children and adolescents to commit crimes on a large scale, protecting themselves under the aegis of the age of criminal responsibility, where these individuals, minors, are beyond *the legitimate protection of the State*, the same State that condemned them to a natural, phylogenetic and ontogenetic state of misery and social malaise.

This one here perhaps represents the most complex situation to analyze regarding public policies aimed at children and youth, because although there is a set of them, all very well elaborated and ratified by international organizations, those who actually need support, care and special protection from the State are the families, and it is the family, through its welfare state, that must guarantee the affective, physical and psychological security of minors, who are vulnerable by nature as a species, and who do not fall into a state of social vulnerability.

The State is an abstract entity, and all its bureaucratic agents are figures foreign to children. No matter how interested they may be in helping, they will never be able to gain the children's trust, considering that this trust is given to them through the mother's discourse. In other words, she, as well as the father and siblings, are individuals with whom a close affective and responsible bond is formed, becoming real, present entities—a psychic link that transcends the dimension of the blood relationship that unites them.

1. Unable to even make this phylogenetic interpretation regarding the human species and its psychosocial development processes, bureaucrats begin to appeal to semantics as a way to *humanize* relationships. Kant (1724-1804) already argued:
2. 'Legal scholars are still searching for their concept of law.' In Dante Alighieri's view: 'Law is the personal or real proportion, from Man to Man, which, when

preserved, preserves society; when corrupted, corrupts it.' An in-depth analysis of the various meanings of the word Law has shown that they correspond to three basic aspects, discernible at any moment in legal life: a normative aspect (Law as an order and its respective science); a factual aspect (Law as a fact, or in its social and historical effectiveness); and an axiological aspect (Law as a value of justice) (Florêncio, 2005, p. 187).

They classify as effective public policies the fact of no longer referring to the delinquent as such; instead, they should be called a *minor in conflict with the law*, and cannot simply be called a minor, because the epithet helps to differentiate them from those minors who are not in such aggravated situations. This already creates two categories: the minor who is so classified by law, to whom the State and its benefits, as well as its technicians and bureaucrats, are always absent; and the minor, the one interpreted as a delinquent, for whom the State and all its protective apparatus is always ready to defend from the wrath of society.

It should be clarified that the expression "*minor*," to which so much reference is made in this work, began to be frequently used in Brazilian legal vocabulary from the late 19th and early 20th centuries. According to Lodoño (1996), from 1920 to the present day, it has come to refer to and indicate children in situations of abandonment and marginalization, in addition to defining their civil and legal status and the rights that correspond to them.

One point that needs clarification is that it is not necessarily the absence of public policies aimed at protecting children and youth that predisposes them to juvenile delinquency; it is much more the lack of economic infrastructure in families that weighs most heavily on this situation, in particular. Most of the time, parents are aware of their sons' and daughters' criminal activities; but they remain silent because they depend on their earnings for the *survival* of the household. In many situations where these [*still*] adolescents are killed in conflicts with state forces, there are protests from family members not because they have lost a son or a brother, but because they have lost someone who was the sole provider for the family. The human maternal-filial bond ceases to exist when misery and the wind of imminent death blow towards them.

The government reports highlighting the neglect of children and adolescents are very interesting, causing state and para-state bodies that oppress and repress parents and guardians who fail to comply with the law to become executioners, fostering the creation of harsher laws against them; however, there is no analysis of the sociological conditions of families, such as employment, housing, basic sanitation, treated water, health, leisure, and well-being. If the family has a refrigerator, electricity, a gas stove, and a television, they are classified as middle class; but no census technician dares to ask if that same refrigerator is full or empty.

Thus, delinquency is not, *per se*, the cause of violence; it is both a cause and a consequence, understanding the absence of public policies as symbolic violence against the law-abiding citizen, placing them on a knife's edge, destined for a double condemnation: first, to be rendered invisible by the State so that it does not have to spend its savings, and then to be hunted by the State so that security and peace can be guaranteed. Ultimately, what we have is that the State creates the monsters that it will later hunt and exterminate as proof of its efficiency [*or deficiency*] in protecting its citizens, who do not feel disappointed in terms of abandonment and lack of security in every sense.

Juvenile Delinquents and Their Judges from a Legal Perspective

This is perhaps one of the most violent and complex premises that Social Psychology must grapple with in an attempt to understand juvenile delinquency: who are the judges who will decide the fate of such individuals? It is a strange paradox to discuss; but the State and its entire body of agents act negligently towards the entire population, especially children and adolescents, and only after they commit any type of delinquent and/or criminal act does the State intervene, in a childish attempt to restore order. This individual was a completely anonymous figure in society, who could not count on any kind of defense against the abuses he suffered, ranging from his misery to physical and psychological aggression and torture.

However, it is enough for him to transgress the law for him to be recognized as someone who lacks the necessary moral support to follow the path of good and justice, and if he was thrown into the world and underworld of crime, it was not by his deliberate will; therefore, he must be protected from the wrath of society and the arbitrariness of the State, and he should be given not a sanction or a penalty commensurate with the harm caused to third parties or to public property, but a condition of dignity, a form of moral reparation, for having followed that nefarious path; that is, the blame for the minor's delinquent behavior is surreptitiously imputed to the State and Society.

Thus, from a legal perspective, the analysis to be made is not about who the judges are, but rather the defenders; because judgment has already been discarded by the legislator when drafting the statute that guarantees the inviolable rights of minors in conflict with the law. What follows is not individuals or state agents concerned with the well-being of the child or adolescent under the law; they are very concerned with ensuring that the law is respected; because it is this indelible respect for the law, in relation to the accused, that guarantees the *legitimacy of democracy*.

Surrounded by all this loving and affectionate apparatus, the delinquent feels, deep down, that crime pays; because before he was beaten, violated, kicked, insulted and chased away and there was no one to intervene on his behalf, and it was enough for him to commit a criminal act that, *voilà*, he became a celebrity, receiving everything that a decent human being enjoys by natural right and that is guaranteed in the constitution of his country, which he completely ignores, but which he learned to hear so often after going from victim to aggressor. He was, until the moment of his capture, like that bush that grows in the middle of the road and that everyone passes by and throws from one side to the other, because, as J.J. Rousseau states in his classic *Emile* (1762),

Given the state of affairs, a man left to his own devices from birth, among others, would be the most disfigured of all. Prejudices, authority, necessity, example, all the social institutions in which we find ourselves submerged would stifle nature within him and put nothing in its place. It would be like a bush that chance caused to sprout in the middle of the road and that passersby will soon kill, beating it from all sides and bending it in every direction (Rousseau, 2009, p. 11).

However, what is striking is that those who consider themselves his defenders become his judges, attributing to him that he became aggressive because of his social circumstances, in which he lacked the best conditions of love and affection; nevertheless, he cannot be considered a bad individual, it is enough that he is given all the love that was denied him in childhood and he will be renewed; this is because these illustrious scholars believe, with such tenacity, that they are still pure and innocent children that they defend them as such. Contrary to such a puerile belief, in *Emile et Sophie*, Rousseau himself (2011) affirms how naive human beings are in believing that a harmonious home is capable of supporting those who never experienced it in their childhood, and we are not talking about a home; but in shelters where others are, in many cases, serving *socio-educational measures* for having committed offenses and/or crimes far more serious than his.

One situation that needs clarification is that children subjected to stressful environments develop a capacity to cope with adverse situations, a special condition of psychic mutation that transforms them into beings unrecognizable from the generic behavioral point of view of the species. Human beings, when in extreme situations, do things that defy the Cartesian positivist logic that fills books, manuals, and the supposed knowledge of professionals in the fields of humanities and psychological sciences.

The biggest mistake made in the treatment and trial of juvenile delinquents is to treat their psychology in the same way as that of a child from a traditional family, and from this

grotesque error try to analyze the situation in search of a solution for the minor, believing that he is emotionally disturbed by the harm he caused the victim.

At a certain point in their lives, crimes become part of their routine and their guarantee of survival, to the point of becoming a form of pleasure, an inherent need for their psycho-emotional well-being. It is based on this process of epigenetic mutation that this essay argues for the extinction of the age of criminal responsibility, because in this way, the magistrate would be free to disregard the pedagogical and psychologizing literature [*based on Rousseauian doctrine* , which dominated the market; texts that only serve to obscure judgment and cloud the decision] and demand empirical studies that demonstrate results from the psychology of the subject itself, namely, the minor who commits delinquent offenses. Whenever captured and brought to trial, the first thing the judges ask is whether the minor is repentant for what they did and the harm they caused. The first time they are confronted with this question, it seems strange to them; But, with time, he learns that all he has to do is play the game the bureaucrats want him to play for everything to work in his favor, and at a certain point, being caught becomes part of his enjoyment. It is no longer the justice system that subjects him to its judgment, but rather he who determines how they will behave in his presence.

Nietzsche (2007, p. 78) argues that "true remorse is extremely rare, particularly among wrongdoers and criminals"; because, as their delinquent acts become mere games, to repent of them would mean denying their happiness, which they will not do, since they are only recognized as someone by society and the State when they break the law. Respecting the law, they are nothing more than an invisible figure, abandoned to their own fate or the misfortune of existence and life.

By breaking with the institution of the age of criminal responsibility, a juvenile delinquent would no longer be treated as a defenseless child before the authorities and the judge. They would be forced to treat themselves as someone who knows the limits of the law and justice, and at the same time, it would oblige the State to invest in the necessary social spaces to minimize acts of violence against human dignity.

CONCLUSION

Throughout this essay, we have sought to clarify that the institution of the age of criminal responsibility no longer holds up as a contribution to the right to protect the well-being of children and adolescents, because it has become a space where delinquents themselves have come to exert dominance, using the established norms to manipulate decisions against

themselves; in other words, they have learned to determine how the game is played and to what extent, making it seem as if everything is about protecting their subjective right to justice.

Since its inception in the 1920s, its existence has been justified because Sociology, Psychology, and Psychiatry were nothing more than primitive scientific projects. Sociology lacked the capacity to assess the true extent of the impact of economics and deprivation on the formation of individual character and personality. Psychology wasn't even considered a science, and Brazil never invested sufficiently in experimental psychological research aimed at deepening knowledge about epigenetic changes resulting from conflict situations and the extent of their impact on individual thought and behavior. Finally, Psychiatry was not yet concerned with criminality as a behavioral condition, taking sociological issues as its starting point.

The moment when the legal concept of lowering the age of criminal responsibility came into being in Brazil represents a form of protection for children and adolescents from absolute and unrestricted ignorance about the endogenous and exogenous factors that led individuals to a state of criminality. This is a laudable situation when analyzed within a historical context; however, with the advancement of medical, social, and psychological sciences, coupled with improvements in living conditions—that is, with the creation of public policies that would meet the population's demands in terms of social security—the expectation was that there would be an automatic reduction in the rate of violence, especially regarding juvenile delinquency.

That is not what happened, and even with the draconian style of overprotection of childhood and adolescence imposed on society through the Statute of the Child and Adolescent (Law 8069/1990), acts of juvenile delinquency not only increased in quantity but also in algebraic proportion, in terms of symbolic violence and the instilling of terror in the frightened and defenseless victims of such individuals, considered *minors* by the justice system and elevated to the *status quo* of victims of society; a very dangerous thought, because if they are considered as such, what they are practicing can be interpreted as a punishment against society and, semantically, this word means *retribution*.

Therefore, by referring to juvenile offenders as *mere victims of society*, they are being granted a justified freedom to act according to their most primitive, insane, and excessive desires. This expression remains firmly entrenched within the framework of the concept of the age of criminal responsibility, where, on one hand, justice is muzzled in its power of direct and indirect action, and on the other, the [*supposed*] defenders of human rights, who have already demonstrated the most absolute ignorance about human behavior and social psychology, treat delinquents as innocent, pious creatures who act without any notion of the harm caused to others and to themselves.

At the other extreme, and no less important, are the organized groups that recruit and entice minors into the world of delinquency. Protected by the sovereignty of the law as legally unaccountable, these minors become perfect instruments for maintaining disorder disguised as protection for the vulnerable. Despite advancements in social and medical sciences, the justification that judges act against the law, invoking popular vengeance against the offender, no longer applies. Examinations, tests, and evaluations can provide a fair measure of the offender's level of understanding and awareness of their offense and the extent of the harm caused to the victims.

In the field of human and social sciences, especially with regard to the spectrum of law, the end of a particular legal institution never signifies losses in terms of the protection of law. *Naturalism*, always considering that the interest of justice is, in short, to protect society as a whole and not, particularly, the individual and collectives. The end of the institution of the age of criminal responsibility, the subject discussed here and the focus of this essay, aims to protect society from the hidden interests of groups that have become manipulators of justice, taking as an object of individual protection a cause that, *a priori*, and in primitive times of Brazilian justice, demonstrated [*or seemed*] to be of a noble nature.

REFERENCES

ANDRADE FILHO, Arício da Silva. *The constitutionality of reducing the initial term of criminal majority*. [Published on 04/16/2007]. Available at: <https://jus.com.br/artigos/9749/a-constitucionalidade-da-reducao-do-termo-inicial-da-maioridade-penal>. Accessed on 01/02/2025.

BRAZIL. *Military Criminal Procedure Code*. **Decree-Law No. 1,002, of October 21, 1969.**

FLORENCIO, Gilbert RL. *New legal dictionary*. 2nd ed. São Paulo: LED, 2005.

GONZÁLEZ, Ernesto Pérez. *Psychology : criminal law and criminology*. La Habana: Ediciones ONBC, 2012.

LODOÑO, Fernando T. The Origin of the Minor Concept. In: PRIORE, Mary Del (org.) *History of the Child in Brazil*. São Paulo: Contexto, 1992.

NIETZSCHE, Friedrich Wilhelm. *On the Genealogy of Morality*. São Paulo: Escala, 2007. Second Treatise: "Fault," "Bad Conscience," and Related Phenomena. Af. 14.

ROUSSEAU, Jean-Jacques. *Emile, or On Education*. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2009. [Book originally published in 1762].

ROUSSEAU, Jean-Jacques. *Emile and Sophie or The Solitaries*. São Paulo: Hedra, 2011. First Letter. [Written in 1762. First published by Moltou and Du Peyrou in *Collection complete des oeuvres by JJ Rousseau*, in 1780].

SOUZA, Etelma Tvaes de. *From the doctrine of irregular situation to the doctrine of integral protection* (2002). PUC-SP. Available at: www.sosbrasil.org.br . Accessed on 16/01/2025.